

Research Article

Development And Evaluation Of Hydrolyzed Graft Copolymer Based Hydrogel Of Ornidazole For Treatment Of Periodontal Disease

Neha Prajapati*

Shree Dhanvantary Pharmacy College, Kim, Surat, Gujarat

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 21 Sep 2024

Accepted: 25 Sep 2024

Published: 06 Oct 2024

Keywords:

Periodontitis, Grafting, High performance biopolymer, Mucoadhesive gel, Sustainability.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.13895785

ABSTRACT

Periodontitis is an inflammatory and plaque induced condition leading to the progressive and episodic loss of tooth attachment apparatus, for which intrapocket devices have gained the most preference. In this study, natural polysaccharide starch has been grafted with acrylamide monomer by microwave assisted grafting method using ammonium persulfate as a chemical initiator. Four sets of Ornidazole mucoadhesive gels (6% w/v) viz. F1, F2, F3 and F4 were prepared from hydrolyzed copolymers (GH1-GH4) respectively. The procedure and results for preparation of hydrolyzed graft copolymers and their evaluations are explained in reference 1. The gels were evaluated for pH, viscosity, thermal analysis, syringeability, spreadability, mucoadhesive strength, in vitro drug release and kinetic model application. All the formulations were found to be diffusion controlled and among all formulations, set F1 was proved to be most promising in terms of mucoadhesive strength (6.5 ± 0.0553) and in-vitro diffusion (95.29% in 8 h) of drug.

INTRODUCTION

The term periodontitis is derived from three words: 'Peri' (around), 'odont' (tooth) and 'itis' (inflammation). In Periodontal disease, an inflammatory process involving progressive and episodic loss of periodontal attachment apparatus occurs, resulting ultimately in tooth loss in susceptible patients. This disease results from the host response to bacterial antigen and irritants and involves periodical accumulation of bacterial biofilms, which is mostly an anaerobic

microorganisms². Periodontal diseases are generally divided in to two groups: Gingivitis – amilder form and Periodontitis – a serious oral health condition. Periodontitis can cause deep pockets infection, which may result in the loss of teeth and their surrounding bone if it is left untreated³. Majorly responsible microorganisms are Actinobacillus actinomycetemcomitans, Prevotella intermedia, Porphyromonas gingivalis, Spirochetes, Bacteroids forsythus and

*Corresponding Author: Neha Prajapati

Address: Shree Dhanvantary Pharmacy College, Kim, Surat, Gujarat

Email ✉: nmjain298@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Fusobacterium are the major responsible microorganisms for the periodontal diseases⁴.

Various surgical approaches are used for the treatment of periodontal diseases like Scaling and root planning, Bone/Tissue grafts, Flap surgery etc^{5,6}. The surgical therapies are unable to remove microorganisms completely as they remain in the debris after surgery. This emerges a need to combine various systemic and/or local delivery systems with the surgical one⁵. Various systemic delivery systems of Tetracyclin Hcl, Metronidazole, Doxycycline etc. are available having various disadvantages of systemic side effects, toxicities, higher dose and dose frequency, low patient compliance, first pass metabolism etc⁵. "These disadvantages of systemic therapy directed us to go for the local therapies which avoid these many disadvantages^{7,8}. In comparison to solid devices, semisolid (gel) formulations have an advantages, such as, relatively faster release of the incorporated drug (particularly with respect to powders, fibres or microparticles); ease of preparation; ease of administration; high biocompatibility and mucoadhesivity (which allow the adhesion to the mucosa in the dental pocket and rapid elimination through normal catabolic pathways), decreasing the risk of irritative or allergic host reactions at the application site⁹. Controlled/sustained release formulations such as bio/muco- adhesive systems, prepared using various natural polysaccharides have gained an immense attention due to their

sustainability, biodegradability, economy and safety over comparable synthetic materials. This study uses modified natural polysaccharide starch.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Drug Ornidazole was obtained as a gift sample from Veteran Pharma, Ahmedabad. All the other ingredients used were of analytical grade, and were used as procured.

Methods

Formulation Development

Determination of λ_{max} :

A drug solution of 14 μ g/ml was prepared in phosphate buffer pH 6.6 and UV spectra were performed between 400-200 nm to determine absorption maxima (λ_{max}).

Calibration study of Ornidazole:

Accurately 100 mg of Ornidazole was weighed and dissolved in 100 ml of phosphate buffer pH 6.6 to prepare a stock solution A. From it, sequential dilutions were performed to prepare working standards; 2 μ g/ml to 20 μ g/ml concentrations. The absorbance was measured using UV spectrophotometer at 317 nm.

Preparation of drug loaded gel:

Calculated amount of hydrolyzed copolymer was dissolved in deionized water to prepare 6% w/v polymeric solution. After complete dissolution, the drug (10% w/w of polymer) was added to polymeric solution; mixed properly; and the whole mixture was kept overnight to equilibrate.

Table 1. Formulations of Hydrogels

Formulations	Code of Hydrolyzed Graft Copolymer used ¹	% Grafting of used copolymer ¹	Concentration of polymeric solution (%w/v)	Amount of drug Added (%w/w of polymer)
F1	GH1	349.5	6	10
F2	GH2	315.5	6	10
F3	GH3	285.5	6	10
F4	GH4	212	6	10

Evaluations of Hydrogel formulations:

pH11:

Each formulation was evaluated for its pH by using a digital glass electrode pH meter. The pH meter was first calibrated using standard buffer capsules pH 4.0 and 9.0. Then the pH was measured by bridging the electrode near the surface of gel and allowing it to equilibrate for a minute.

Rheological study12:

The Brookfield rheometer was used to study viscosity of each formulation. The viscosities have been measured using spindle S 61 at different rpm at 27°C.

Compatibility study13:

To ensure the compatibility in formulation, FTIR spectra of drug ornidazole and formulation was carried out using KBr pallet method.

Thermal analysis10,11:

Differential scanning calorimetry of pure drug and formulation was performed up to the temperature of 600°C. The heating rate was uniform in all cases at 10°C/min.

Syringeability study14:

The time required to squeeze out 1 ml of gel from the syringe with 22 gauge needle was estimated. The more viscous the gel, higher will be the duration. The viscosity of gel must be such that it should comfortably squeezed out during syringe application.

Spreadability study15:

1 g of gel was placed on the centre of glass plate (20 cm × 20 cm). The other glass plate of the same size was then carefully placed upon it and a weight of 100g was applied for a minute to remove the entrapped air. The diameter of spreaded gel (d mm) was accurately measured and the spreading area was calculated by using following equation:

Spreading area

$$(\text{mm}^2) = d^2 \times \pi / 4$$

Mucoadhesive strength9:

This study was performed using modified apparatus. It is comprised of a two arm balance, one side of which contained two glass plates and the other side contained a container. One of the two glass plates was attached permanently to the base of the stage, and the other was attached to the arm of the balance by a thick strong thread. The membrane used for mucoadhesive testing was fresh rabbit intestinal membrane. Fresh rabbit intestine was glued to the upper side of the lower plate and another was glued to the lower side of the upper plate by using cyanoacrylate adhesive. The weighed gel (0.1 g) was placed on the rabbit intestine glued to the upper side of the lower plate. Then, the upper plate was placed over the lower plate and 50 g preload force was applied for 5 min (preload time). After removal of the preload force, the water, kept in a burette at some height, was siphoned into the container at a rate of 10 ml per minute till the plates were detached from each other. The weight of water (g) required for the detachment of the glass plates was considered as the mucoadhesion force of the applied gel.

Drug content analysis:

Accurately 1g of gel was weighed and dissolved in 100 ml of phosphate buffer pH 6.6. Drug content analysis was carried out by preparing stock solution as per the below mentioned scheme by further dilutions, to achieve the concentrations in calibration range using UV spectrophotometer. The drug content was found by using following equation:

$$\text{Concentration } (\mu\text{g/ml}) = (\text{Absorbance/ slope}) \times \text{Dilution factor}$$

In vitro diffusion study9:

Diffusion study was carried out using Dialysis sac method. Dialysis sac of average diameter 15.9 mm was taken. Briefly 2 ml of formulation was placed in the dialysis sac hermetically sealed at one end and open at another. The sac was then folded and hermetically sealed to close both the ends. This “dialysis bag” was then emerged with the help of

a thread into a beaker containing 50 ml of phosphate buffer pH 6.6 as diffusion media maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ on a magnetic stirrer. Aliquots of 5 ml was withdrawn periodically at suitable time intervals and every time equal volume was replaced with fresh phosphate buffer pH 6.6 maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. The amount of drug release was measured by taking absorbance using UV spectrophotometer at 317 nm.

Kinetic models application16:

To understand the drug release mechanism from the developed formulation following kinetic models were applied.

- i. Higuchi model
- ii. Zero order release model

- iii. First order release model
- iv. Kosmeyer-Peppas model

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Determination of λ_{max} and calibration curve:

The UV spectrum run for a drug solution (14 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) shows a sharp peak at 317 nm in phosphate buffer pH 6.6. Hence this is taken as a working λ_{max} throughout the study for drug estimation. Further a calibration curve plotted taking concentration on X axis and absorbance on a Y axis shows a linear relationship for drug solution with regression coefficient of 0.9991. The drug working standards between the range 2-20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ followed the Beer-Lamberts law.

Conc($\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$)	Absorbance
2	0.087 (± 0.002)
4	0.159 (± 0.002)
6	0.243 (± 0.002)
8	0.317 (± 0.002)
10	0.405 (± 0.001)
12	0.5 (± 0.001)
14	0.585 (± 0.001)
16	0.675 (± 0.001)
Equation	$Y=0.0426x-0.0117$
Regression Coefficient (R^2)	0.9991

Compatibility Study:

FTIR of Pure drug Ornidazole

FTIR of Formulation

IR spectra of Ornidazole:

The peaks at 3165.29 cm⁻¹ and 3311.89 cm⁻¹ are attributed to O-H stretching. The characteristic peaks, at 3114.18 cm⁻¹ and 3091.03 cm⁻¹ are due to C-H stretching. As this drug is from the class 5-nitroimidazole, the distinctive sharp peaks at 1536.35 cm⁻¹, 1362.75 cm⁻¹, 1272.10 cm⁻¹ and 829.42 cm⁻¹ are due to -NO₂ stretching. The same peak at wave number 829.42 cm⁻¹ also indicates C-N stretching. Further a sharp peak at 1151.54 cm⁻¹ is assigned to C-O stretching.

IR spectra of Formulation:

All the characteristic peaks of drug ornidazole i.e., for O-H stretching (3313.82 cm⁻¹), C-H stretching (3090.07 cm⁻¹), -NO stretching (1536.35 cm⁻¹, 1361.79 cm⁻¹, 1268.24 cm⁻¹ and 828.45 cm⁻¹), C-N stretching (828.45 cm⁻¹) and C-O stretching (1150.58 cm⁻¹) is present in IR spectrum of formulation along with the peaks of polymer such as 1675.23 cm⁻¹ for C=O stretching and at 1427.37 cm⁻¹ for COO- stretching. This concludes

that there is no interaction between drug and polymer and thus are compatible with each other. Differential scanning calorimetry of Ornidazole and Formulation has been performed up to the temperature of 350°C. The heating rate was uniform in all cases at 10°C/min.

DSC spectra of pure drug (Ornidazole)11,19

DSC Spectra of Formulation

With respect to literature review, the endothermic peak of pure drug Ornidazole has been obtained at 90.87°C. The endothermic peak of Ornidazole in formulation shows no significant change indicating compatibility.

Preparation of gel formulation:

Four sets of gel formulations F1 to F4 were prepared using graft copolymer G1-G4 and evaluated for various parameters. The physical appearance of gels has been shown in the figure

Figure 1 Gel Formulations F1 to F4

Evaluations of formulations:

Table 1 Evaluations of formulations

Code	pH	Spreading area (mm ²)	Syringeability test (s)	Mucoadhesive strength (g)	Drug content(%)
F1	7.1	2826.00±0.48	61	6.5 ±0.05	101.0±0.055
F2	7.1	3115.66±0.53	51	5.9 ±0.06	102.5±0.064
F3	7.3	3419.46±0.67	45	4.5 ±0.20	102.1±0.058
F4	7.2	6079.04±0.34	34	3.0 ±0.40	101.7±0.063

From the results of pH determination, it can be seen that pH of all developed formulation ranged between 7.1-7.3, which is neutral and hence would be avoiding the risk of irritation to the mucosal surface of tooth pocket. Spreadability study has been characterized in terms of spreading area. The results show that the spreading area increases from F1 to F4. This result can be attributed to the viscosity of developed gels. As formulation F1 is prepared with highly grafted polymer, it has the highest viscosity and less spreadability. The viscosity gradually decreased from the formulation F2 to F4 which is reflected well in its spreadability. A less spreadability may sometime be useful for a long retention time in gum pockets. Syringeability study is required to confirm ease of

squeezing out of formulation from syringe during its administration to the patient. Further like spreadability the viscosity of the formulation affected its syringeability. From the result it can be seen that all formulations were easily syringeable within the time range of a minute. Formulation with good mucoadhesive strength can retain for longer period of time. Mucoadhesivity study ensured that all the formulations has good mucoadhesive strength and therefore can retain for longer period of time. Above data indicates that the formulation F1 has the highest mucoadhesivity, and F4 has the lowest. This result is in good agreement with the spreadability and viscosity study. Mucoadhesive strength decreases with decrease in the % grafting. It can be due to

higher number of mucoadhesive carboxylic groups with increased % grafting. Finally drug content analysis study showed that all formulation has uniform drug content between 101-102.5%. The proper and homogeneous distribution of drug throughout the gel is essential for the uniform administration of drug to the patient.

Rheological study17:

Pseudoplastic flow is typically exhibited by polymers in solution. The viscosity of a

pseudoplastic material cannot be explained by a single value, because no part of the curve is linear. The most satisfactory representation for a pseudoplastic material however is probably a graphical plot of the entire consistency curve. In this study, the rheology of prepared modified polymers has been performed by measuring the shear stress at different shear rates. Rheological data of 2% solutions of each hydrolyzed copolymer has been obtained as below:

Table 2 Rheological study of gel formulations

Shear rate (rpm)	F1 (cps)	F2 (cps)	F3 (cps)	F4 (cps)
0.3	4399	3439	1848	455.9
0.5	4259	3409	1292	439
0.6	4059	3395	1260	422.9
1.0	3941	3053	1220	419.9
1.5	3522	2951	1080	410.9
2.0	3012	2822	980	359.9

Results show that all the polymeric solutions exhibit pseudoplastic flow. From the prepared 4 sets, Formulation F1 has highest apparent viscosity. This is attributed to the same concept of charge repulsion as discussed before in the section

of intrinsic viscosity. More repulsion can be achieved with increased %grafting, which results in decreased apparent viscosity from F1 to F4.

In vitro diffusion study:

Table 3 In vitro drug release study

Time (min)	% Cumulative Drug Release(%CDR)			
	F1	F2	F3	F4
15	18.10±0.37	19.51±0.42	20.39±0.66	22.24±0.87
30	27.31±0.64	30.53±0.83	29.12±0.49	32.47±0.74
60	35.48±0.46	42.62±0.74	44.94±0.39	42.97±0.67
120	48.63±0.47	56.52±0.46	57.58±0.78	58.63±0.64
180	59.96±0.53	67.92±0.74	72.14±0.83	74.49±0.77
240	68.41±0.38	75.66±0.54	86.17±0.38	82.83±0.89
300	75.98±0.63	82.39±0.23	91.94±0.73	96.33±0.78
360	83.35±0.58	88.97±0.42	96.89±0.78	-
420	89.24±0.62	95.63±0.64	-	-
480	95.29±0.69	-	-	-

From the data shown in table 3.3 it can be seen that, all the gels were successfully sustained the drug release for the period between 5-8h. Further the % drug release increased from F1 to F4. Formulation F1 released its content for longest period of time (8h). Result shows that inverse

correlation exists between % grafting and drug release from the formulations. As the %grafting increases % drug release decreases. Thus it shows direct correlation between % grafting and sustainability of formulation.

Kinetic models:

Table 4 Comparison of regression coefficients

Formulation code	Higuchi model (R ²)	Zero order Release (R ²)	First order release Model (R ²)	Kosmeyer- Peppas model	
				(R ²)	Slope
F1	0.9991	0.9262	0.9616	0.9951	0.4674
F2	0.9941	0.8948	0.9653	0.9888	0.5084
F3	0.9954	0.9111	0.9753	0.9899	0.5118
F4	0.9981	0.948	0.9198	0.9961	0.4599

Comparison of regression coefficient of each model shows that Higuchi model gives highest Regression coefficient (R²). Thus, all formulations are diffusion controlled. Further, slopes obtained in Kosmeyer-Peppas model predict that they all follow Fickian diffusion. It means during in vitro diffusion of each formulation, drug molecules diffuses from the region of higher concentration to one of the lower concentration until equilibrium is attained and the rate of diffusion is directly proportional to the concentration gradient across the membrane¹⁸.

CONCLUSION

All the formulations successfully sustained the drug release up to several hours and are diffusion controlled. A good correlation between % grafting and sustainability of formulations existed. Study showed that the matrix composition has a direct effect on the overall formulation performance and in vitro drug release profile. In conclusion modified starch based matrix hold the good potential for further research in the area of novel drug delivery and in treatment of periodontal therapy.

REFERENCES

1. Prajapati N. Development and Evaluation of Mucoadhesive Graft Copolymer of a Natural Polysaccharide Using Microwave Assisted Grafting Technique and Alkaline Hydrolysis. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Technology*. 2024 Sep 6;11(4):428–33.
2. Francis G, Teresa B. The pathogenesis and treatment of periodontal disease. *The academy of dental therapeutics and stomatology*. 1-10.
3. Everyday Health: Trusted Medical Information, Expert Health Advice, News, Tools, and Resources. *EverydayHealth.com*. 2018.
4. K. I. Sameer, Mathew V. Periodontal strips – A newer approach for site specific drug delivery for periodontitis. *B.Pharm projects and review articles*. 2006;1:1382-1496.
5. S P, S A, S K. Recent advances in periodontal drug delivery systems. *International Journal of Drug Delivery*. 2009 Jul 5;1(1):1–14.
6. Cortellini P. Reconstructive periodontal surgery: A challenge for modern periodontology. *International Dental Journal*. 2006 Aug;56:250–5.
7. Schwach-Abdellaoui K. Local delivery of antimicrobial agents for the treatment of periodontal diseases. *European Journal of Pharmaceutics and Biopharmaceutics*. 2000 Jul 3;50(1):83–99.
8. Walker C, Karpinia K. Rationale for use of antibiotics in periodontitis. *Periodontal*, 2008 Oct; 73(10):1188-1196.
9. Bansai K, Rawat M, Singh S. Development of Satranidazole mucodhesive gel for the treatment of periodontitis. *American*

- Association of Pharmaceutical Scientists. 2009 Sept; 10(3):716-723.
10. Mishra S, Mukul A, Sen G, Jha U. Microwave assisted synthesis of polyacrylamide grafted starch (St-g-PAM) and its applicability as flocculant for water treatment. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*. 2011 Jan;48(1):106–11.
 11. Shukla V, Bhardwaj V. Preparation and evaluation of periodontal gel of Ornidazole using natural polymers. *Scholar Research Library*. 2010;2(1):61-69.
 12. Ahmed M, Rompicharla N. Development and evaluation of in situ gels of Moxifloxacin for the treatment of periodontitis. *Indonesia J. Pharm*. 2012;23(3):141-146.
 13. Patel P, Roy A, Kulkarni M. Formulation and evaluation of colon targated tablets of Ornidazole for the treatment of amoebiasis. *International Journal of Drug Development and Research*. 2011 Jan-March;3(1):52-61.
 14. Yellanki S, Singh J. Formulation, characterization and evaluation of Metronidazole gel for local treatment of periodontitis. *International Journal of Pharma and Biosciences*. 2010;1(2):1-9.
 15. Garg A, Aggrawal D, Garg S. Spreading of semisolid formulations. *Pharmaceutical Technology*. 2002 Sept;85-98.
 16. Costa P, Lobo J. Review on modeling and comparison of dissolution profiles. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2001;13:123-133.
 17. Patrick J. *Martin's Physical Pharmacy And Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 5th Edn, Lippincott Williams and Wilkins. London. 2006:561-583.
 18. Brahmanekar DM. Jaiswal SB., *Biopharmaceutics and Pharmacokinetics-A Treatise*. Vallabh Prakashan. 1995; 8-25.

HOW TO CITE: Neha Prajapati, Development And Evaluation Of Hydrolyzed Graft Copolymer Based Hydrogel Of Ornidazole For Treatment Of Periodontal Disease, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2024, Vol 2, Issue 10, 297-306. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13895785>